

Respiratory Manifestations of Near Hanging Patients Presenting to A Tertiary Care Hospital- A One-Year Prospective StudyNibedita Panda¹, Sampat Dash², Satya Ranjan Mohanty³, Ambika Prasad Nayak⁴¹PG Resident, Department of Pulmonary Medicine, Ashwini Hospital, Cuttack²Senior Consultant, Department of Pulmonary Medicine, Ashwini Hospital, Cuttack³Senior Consultant, Department of Pulmonary Medicine, Ashwini Hospital, Cuttack⁴PG Resident, Department of Pulmonary Medicine, Ashwini Hospital, Cuttack

Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 26-07-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Hanging is a prevalent method of ending one's life, which can result in various pulmonary complications such as post-obstructive pulmonary edema, aspiration pneumonia, acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), pneumothorax, and cardiogenic pulmonary edema caused by Takotsubo cardiomyopathy. A one-year prospective study was conducted, including all cases of near hanging presented to our center between January 1, 2022, and December 3, 2022. Ten patients were included in the study, ranging in age from 13 to 30 years, and their Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score on presentation varied between 3 and 12. All patients were managed with cervical spine immobilization and other supportive measures, and each underwent computed tomography (CT) of the cervical spine and brain. All ten patients had leukocytosis, tachycardia, and tachypnea, and six required mechanical ventilation, while three required vasopressors. The number of days of mechanical ventilation ranged from 1 to 4 days. One patient developed a rare pneumothorax, while another developed hanging-induced stress cardiomyopathy. Eight patients were discharged in room air, and two died. Recognizing negative-pressure pulmonary edema, which is common in hanging patients and can be mistaken for ARDS, is crucial for pulmonologists. This condition responds well to supportive treatment and differs from ARDS in terms of its treatment effectiveness.

Keywords: Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome, Glasgow Coma Scale, Computed Tomography, Pneumothorax, Cardiomyopathy.

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Introduction

Suicide rates are notably high in low- and middle-income countries, with over one million lives lost annually. India is among the nations with one of the highest suicide rates in the world. In 2021, 1,64,033 people committed suicide in India, with 57% of those deaths resulting from hangings (NCRB figures, August 2022) [1,2]. Hanging, agricultural chemical consumption, self-immolation, and drowning are the most common methods of suicide in India [3].

Hypoxic brain damage is the leading cause of death and disability following hanging, despite hospital therapy reducing mortality in individuals with low first Glasgow coma scores [GCS] [4]. Aggressive resuscitation and medical intervention increase the chances of a positive outcome [5].

The goal of this study is to analyze the demographics and outcomes of patients who present to the adult emergency department of a

tertiary care hospital in Eastern India following a near-hanging incident.

Materials & Methods

Research commenced subsequent to securing approval from the Institutional Ethics Committee. This investigation followed a prospective design, spanning duration of one year.

The study encompassed all instances of near hanging incidents that were presented to Ashwini Hospital, Cuttack, between January 1, 2022, and December 3, 2022. A total of ten patients were enrolled in the study, who was admitted to our emergency department during the timeframe. The necessary consent was obtained from the patients' parents. The cases were evaluated based on the symptoms and findings observed in the lungs.

Statistical Analysis: The statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS software, version 16.0, developed by SPSS Inc. in Chicago. The mean and

standard deviation of continuous variables were calculated, and the chi-square test or Fisher's exact test was used to compare the proportional expressions of categorical variables. A two-sided P value of 0.05 or less was considered statistically significant for all tests.

Results

The data of the study population can be seen in Table 1. In the span of a year, ten cases involving near-hanging situations were reported to the center. The remaining nine cases were female, while one example was male. Five instances had GCS scores of 8 or lower. Six cases required Mechanical Ventilation (MV) support. Eight out of ten cases made it through the near-hanging ordeal unscathed, while two cases did not.

Table 1: Patient data

Variables	Number	Percentage (%)
Total Sample	10	100
Male : Female	1 : 9	10 : 90
GCS \leq 8 during admission	5 (min 3 Max 14)	50
Vasopressor support	3	30
Invasive Mechanical ventilation (MV)	6	60
Average days on MV support	3 days (Min 1 and Max 4)	
Cervical Spine Injury	1 (Paracentral bulging with indentation at C5-6) on MRI	
Mortality	2	20

Laboratory variables included in the research sample are displayed in Table 2. In seven instances, the white blood cell count was more than 11,000 Cu.mm. In a total of five instances, a pH below 7.35 was noted. Pulmonary edema was noted in seven cases, pneumothorax in one, and a respiratory rate of more than twenty in eight.

Table 2: Laboratory Parameters data

Variables	Number	Percentage (%)
Total Leukocyte Count > 11000	7 cases (Min 8500 & Max 34500)	70
pH 7.35 – 7.45	5	50
pH 7.25 – 7.35	4	40
pH < 7.25	1	10
Lactate > 1.5	6 (Min 8.8 & Max 1.7)	60
pCO ₂ 35 to 45 mm Hg	9	90
pCO ₂ 45 to 60 mm Hg	1	10
pCO ₂ > 60 mm Hg	Nil	0
PaO ₂ / FiO ₂ >300	4	40
300–200	4	40
200 – 100	0	0
< 100	2	20
Respiratory Rate (RR) >20	8	80
Pulmonary Edema	7	70
Pneumothorax	1	10
ECHO (Stress Induced Cardiomyopathy)	1	10

Discussion

The aim of this research was to provide a comprehensive description of the demographic characteristics, hanging mode, complications, and prognosis of patients who presented to a tertiary care hospital in Ashwini Hospital, Cuttack while near hanging. Less than one percent of our emergency department visits were attributed to near hanging, which remains a considerable proportion in comparison to other data that has been published in the literature. The male:female ratio in this research was 1:9, with a female preponderance of 90%. An Indian study indicates that suicides were predominantly committed by females.[2] In India, hanging ranked as the second most prevalent method of death by suicide, with young married

women and unmarried men favouring this approach[2,3]. In contrast to the mean age of 25.33 years reported in our study, the age range of 13 to 30 years was frequently observed in research articles originating from this part [3] In this research, youthful and middle-aged patients resorted to near hanging predominantly. The motives for suicidal hanging varied considerably from nation to nation. The previously cited reasons included alcohol addiction, interpersonal conflicts, impulsive personalities, financial setbacks, academic setbacks, and romantic setbacks [2,3].

According to the findings of a study [4] approximately one-third of patients who arrived at the hospital had a GCS reading of 8 or less, indicating that their prognosis was favorable

despite having a low GCS [5]. In the present investigation, 50 % of the patients exhibited a GCS of higher or equal to 8, with 50 % of them having a very low GCS of 8 or less. Our own outcome of 80% of the patients being evacuated alive validates the results reported in the study by [6]. As reported by Sane et al., hypoxic encephalopathy is a significant contributor to morbidity among patients who are close to hanging [7].

Additionally recognized as a complication of near-hanging victims is pulmonary edema. A total of 70 % of the patients included in this present investigation presented with pulmonary edema like findings [6,7]. Injuries to the cervical spinal cord, status epilepticus, tracheal injuries, and vertebral artery damage are additional uncommon complications of near-hanging that have been documented previously [8-11]. One of the aforementioned uncommon complications (cervical spine injury) was documented in our research.

The mortality rate among near-hanging victims who were transported to the hospital varied from 21% in a Texas-based study to 15% in another study [11-13] We document a 20% mortality rate. 80 % of the patients included in this investigation survived hospital discharge. A mere 60 % of patients required a invasive MV, whereas 39% of patients were admitted for a duration of less than two days.

Even though 74% of patients required intensive care unit admission for interventions such as intubation and mechanical ventilation, number of averages of 3 days on MV. This demonstrates that successful resuscitation, notwithstanding the limited sensorium and poor clinical condition at presentation, yields favorable outcomes.

Conclusion

Among the 10 patients with respiratory manifestations due to hanging, 7 displayed features of pulmonary edema. Although two fatal cases had GCS scores below 8, including one with pneumothorax and the other with stress cardiomyopathy, respiratory symptoms did not directly increase the mortality risk. As a pulmonologist, it is crucial to recognize negative-pressure pulmonary edema, which is common in hanging patients and can be mistaken for ARDS. However, this condition responds well to supportive treatment and differs from ARDS in terms of its treatment effectiveness.

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